

PROSPECTS FOR IMPROVING AND DEVELOPING ONLINE BANKING SERVICES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14749088>

Abstract: The article examines the prospects for improving and developing online banking services in commercial banks of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The state of development of remote banking services in the practice of commercial banks of Uzbekistan is analyzed based on the collected statistical data.

Keywords: remote banking services, internet banking, mobile banking, Bank-client, online banking

The most effective way to ensure the competitiveness of commercial banks is to gain the trust of customers and create all the amenities for them, as well as to increase the type, quality and speed of services. In order to ensure competitiveness, banks are increasingly feeling the need to introduce modern banking services and use new technologies.

In particular, in this regard, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev emphasized in his speech that "... this year we need to take drastic measures to develop the banking system. Starting from 2020, a large-scale transformation program will be implemented in each bank. In this regard, increasing the capital, resource base and income of our banks will be the focus of our special attention" [1].

Taking into account the above, in recent years a number of documents have been adopted aimed at liberalizing the banking system and adapting it to the conditions of free competition. In particular, the adoption of the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 3620 "On additional measures to increase the popularity of banking services" dated March 23, 2018 identified existing problems in the provision of banking services and measures to be taken by banks [2]. In particular, the development and promotion of innovative products for cashless payments, including contactless and mobile technologies; the introduction of contactless and mobile technologies, primarily in the areas of social and household services, transport, trade, catering, especially in the regions; ensuring interaction with international payment systems, etc.

A number of scientists were closely acquainted with the research works of a number of scientists on the topic. They analyzed the opinions of scientists on

remote banking services. In particular, according to the Uzbek economist K. Sattorova: "Remote bank account servicing is a complex of information services and the execution of operations on the client's account based on his instructions without visiting the bank. The remote bank account servicing system is based on the client's application to the bank's database via a telecommunications system" [4].

In recent years, in order to improve the quality of customer service and increase the quality of services provided to them, various innovative banking services have been offered by banks. In particular, the traditional "Bank-Client" system, which provides remote banking services, is widespread in our republic and is implemented in all banks. To use this system, a special program is installed on the client's computer, which provides interaction with the bank's information system through communication channels. However, due to the need to connect to a specific workplace and use specialized programs when using the "Bank-Client" system, the ability to use this system is limited. Therefore, online banking (internet banking) systems are widely used, which work through the Internet and a simple browser, that is, a common program that provides the client with access to the network.

Internet banking technology creates additional conveniences for both the bank and its customers. In particular, the client can perform banking operations on his account from anywhere and at any time via the Internet, without visiting the bank, and can receive information about the status of his account, receipt of funds, and the reflection of payments. This creates the advantages of saving time and money for the client, freely choosing a bank regardless of the distance of the address, and quickly managing his funds. Also, the creation of a national technological platform operating in "on-line" mode in cooperation with commercial banks that are participants in the "Uzcard" interbank payment system will allow the client to manage his card accounts, make utility and other payments in real time through Internet banking services.

As a result of the analysis of the prospects for the development of remote banking services in Uzbekistan, the following proposals and recommendations were developed:

1. Each commercial bank should develop its own strategic program for the development of remote banking services in commercial banks and the development of a remote customer service system. This program should include a roadmap for the step-by-step transition of all types of services to remote and online modes. This roadmap should include the source of financing for the tasks

set, implementation deadlines, the department responsible for implementation, and the project launch date.

2. Currently, the types of services provided remotely by commercial banks include utility and other payments, card-to-card money transfers, online conversion, online deposit services, as well as retail lending services in individual banks, and it is advisable to increase their range at the next stage. In particular, these include the ability to send and receive funds abroad through integration with international money transfers, and the introduction of a virtual issuance service for plastic cards.

3. It is natural that the development of remote banking services creates the need for customer identification. Taking this into account, it would be appropriate to create integration capabilities from the database of the Ministry of Internal Affairs for all mobile banking services when the need arises to identify an employee when providing customer service.

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